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New faunistic and biological records on Coleophoridae from the Balkans (Lepidoptera)

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Abstract. The paper deals with new records on the geographical distribution of 40 species of Coleophoridae in the Balkan area. *Coleophora felixella* Baldizzone, 1994 and *C. goluensis* Baldizzone, 1994 are new for the European fauna. The host plant and the larval case of *C. daglarica* Baldizzone & Tabell, 1999 are presented for the first time.

Keywords. Lepidoptera, Coleophoridae, Balkan area, distributional records, bionomy.

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Introduction

In recent years the Balkan region has been the subject of several entomological research, with particular attention to microlepidoptera. As regards Coleophoridae, some studies have been published that have highlighted the presence of numerous species not yet known for this region, including one new to science, *Coleophora colinplanti* Baldizzone & Richter, 2022 (Richter & Pastorális 2015; Richter 2017, 2018; Baldizzone 2016, 2019b, 2019c, Baldizzone & Richter 2022).

In the following paper, several new distributional data are presented from the two authors' field research and the study of material entrusted to them for determination by various collectors. Two species, *C. felixella* Baldizzone, 1994 and *C. goluensis* Baldizzone, 1994 are new to the European fauna and one, *C. daglarica* Baldizzone & Tabell, 1999 some data on the bionomy provided in a consequence of the discovery of the hostplant and the larva.

Material and methods

Most of the specimens were collected on the sheet with UV lamps or using light traps of various types. The specimens from Albania collected with the traps are almost all in poor condition, so the identification was performed by dissection of the genitalia. The Euparal slide mounts of dissected genitalia were photographed with a Bresser MicroCam II 12 MP attached to a BTC trinocular microscope, mainly using the Nikon 10/0.30 objective. The CombineZP program was used for stacking layers into deep-focus images. The photos were cleaned and edited with Adobe Photoshop version 21.0.2. Adults were photographed with a Canon EOS 600 D digital camera equipped with a Canon MP-E 65 mm objective, with lighting provided by two circular neon lamps OSRAM L 32W / 8400 C (cool white). Morphological terms follow

* Contribution to the knowledge of Coleophoridae CLXIII

Baldizzone (2019a). The genitalia of some specimens are stored in plastic capsules in glycerol.

Abbreviations: Bldz = Giorgio Baldizzone; coll. = collection; det. = determinavit; GP = genital preparation; IgR = Ignác Richter; leg. = legit; TLMF = Tiroler Landesmuseum Ferdinandeum, Innsbruck, Austria.

New distributional records

Coleophora avellanae Tabell & Huemer, 2024 (Figs 3-4.)

Albania: 2 ♂ (GP 35994, 35998 IgR) Tomori Mountain Below Tomori I Madh (above Polican) 686 m, 15.VI.2024, N40.6955: E20.0814, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: The species has been recently described by separating it from *C. milvipennis* Zeller, 1849, based on DNA and anatomical differences in the genitalia. Based on the list of paratypes, the species has been collected in Norway, Italy, Austria, Germany, Hungary, Slovakia, North Macedonia, Russia, but probably the distribution is much wider. First record for Albania.

C. parvicuprella Baldizzone & Tabell, 2006

Albania: 4 ♂ (GP 36006, 36010, 36011, 36012 IgR) Tomori Mts., above Ujanik to Abaz Ali 1894 m, N40.6171, E020.1851, 16.VI.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Italy, Croatia, Greece, North Macedonia, Bulgaria, Turkey (Baldizzone 2019a). First record for Albania.

C. aleramica Baldizzone & Stübner, 2007

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 35996 IgR) Tomori Mountain Below Tomori I Madh (above Polican) 686 m, 15. VI.2024, N40.6955: E20.0814, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant; 1 ♂ (GP 36013 IgR) Tomori Mts., above Ujanik to Abaz Ali 1894 m, N40.6171, E020.1851, 16.VI. 2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter coll. C. W. Plant.; 3 ♂ (GP 35979 IgR) Pogradec Region, Guri I Kamjes, 1341 m, N40°50'37,5'', E020°37'17,4'' 05.VI.2022, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Italy, Sicily, Austria, Slovakia, Hungary, Croatia, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Greece, Turkey, Jordan; recently reported from Spain (Gastón 2024). First record for Albania.

C. ochroflava Toll, 1961

Slovenia: 2 ♂, 7 ♀ Piran, Sečovlje Soline, 5.VII.2023, leg., det., coll. Baldizzone.

Albania: 3 ♀ Fier, Divjakë, 2 m, 40.987646, 19.496382, 18.VIII.2015, leg., coll. F. Graf, det. Tabell & Baldizzone; 1 ♂ Qark Tirana, Rreth-Greth, 3 m, 41.053523, 19.460032, 8.VIII.2024, leg., det., coll. F. Graf.

Distribution: Italy, Bulgaria, Romania, North Macedonia, Greece, Crimea, Russia (Lower Volga), Caucasus (Dagestan, Kabardino-Balkaria, Stavropol distr., Armenia), Turkmenistan (Baldizzone 2024). First record for Slovenia and Albania.

C. serinipennella Christoph, 1872

Albania: 1 ♀ Qark Tirana, Rreth-Greth, 3 m, 41.053523, 19.460032, 1.VI.2023, leg., coll. F. Graf, det. Richter.

Distribution: Spain, Southern France, Southern Italy, Sicily, Slovenia, Bulgaria, Romania, Ukraine, Russia (Lower Volga), Libya, Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt, Palestine, Central Asia, Korea, Japan, and Australia (Baldizzone 2019a). First record for Albania.

C. medelichensis Krone, 1908

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 35983 IgR) Pogradec Region, above Ochrid Lake, below Maja Ahishtes Geges, 1323m, N40.998, E020.6087, 18.VI.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnic-Beshkova, dt. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant; 3 ♂ (GP 35990, 35993, 35997 IgR), Tomori Mountain Below Tomo-

ri I Madh (above Polican) 686 m, 15.VI.2024, N40.6955: E20.0814, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant

Distribution: Spain, France, Italy, Austria, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Slovenia, Croatia, Montenegro, Bulgaria, Greece, Crete, Turkey. Current knowledge on distribution is likely partly incorrect due to identification problems (Baldizzone 2019a). First record for Albania.

C. colutella (Fabricius, 1794)

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 35964 IgR), Prespa Lake, near Globiceni Village, 930m N40.8455, E020.9243, 04.VI.2022, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Almost all of Europe (not present in Great Britain), Caucasus, Iran, USA (introduced) (Baldizzone 2019a). First record for Albania.

C. congeriella Staudinger, 1859

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP35976 IgR) Pogradec Region, Guri I Kamjes, 1314 m, N40°50'37,5'', E020°37'17,4'', 05.VI.2022, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Austria, Slovenia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Bulgaria, North Macedonia, Greece, Turkey, Libya (Baldizzone 2019a). First record for Albania.

C. acrisella Millière, 1872

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP35980 IgR) Pogradec Region, Ochrid Lake, Lin Peninsula 781 m, N41,0587, E020,6481, 24.IX.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant;

1 ♀ (GP 35989 IgR) Pogradec Region, between Dardhas and Guri I Kamjes, 1185 m, N40.8561, E020.631, 23.IX.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant;

1 ♀ (GP 36001 IgR) Liqeni Prespa e Vogel, near Tren Village, 858 m, N40.67466, E020.989, 20.IX.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Portugal, Spain, France, Italy, Austria, Czech Republic, Hungary, Slovenia, Croatia, Greece, Malta, Ukraine (Baldizzone 2019a). First record for Albania.

C. felixella Baldizzone, 1994 (Figs 5-6.)

Greece: 1 ♂ (GP 34452 IgR) Kozani env. 10 km. 4.-10.VI.2021, leg., coll. Srnka, det. Richter.

Distribution: Described from Armenia is known only from the Caucasus (Armenia, Kabardino-Balkaria, Abkhazia) (Anikin & Schurov 2005). First record for Greece and Europe.

C. pulchripennella Baldizzone, 2011

Albania: 1 ♂ Quark Shkodra, Gomsiqe, 590 m, 41.995759, 19.811017, 29.VI.2023, leg., coll. F. Graf, det. Richter, teste Baldizzone.

Distribution: Widespread throughout the Mediterranean region, from the Iberian Peninsula and France to Italy (also Sardinia and Sicily), Croatia, Montenegro, Greece (including Crete and several smaller islands), Malta, Tunisia and Turkey (Baldizzone 2019c). First record for Albania.

C. mareki Tabell & Baldizzone, 2014

Bosnia & Herzegovina: 1 ♀ (GP Bldz 17768) Priluka, Korićna, 1160 m, 20.VIII.2021, leg., coll. T. Koren, det. Baldizzone.

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 35959 IgR) Erseke Region, above Borove Village, 1096 m N40.2977, E020.6594, 21.VII.2022, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkoiva, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant;

2 ♂ (GP 35985, 35987 IgR) Tepelene Region, above Nivice Village, 1150 m, N.40.2679, E019.8864, 04.VII.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant;

2 ♂ (GP 35992, 35999 IgR) Tomori Mountain Below Tomori I Madh (above Polican) 686 m, 15. 6. 2024, N40.6955: E20.0814, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: France, Italy, Sardinia, Austria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Bulgaria, Serbia, Greece, Ukraine, Turkey, Iraq (Baldizzone & Richter 2022). First record for Bosnia & Herzegovina and Albania.

C. serpylletorum E. Hering, 1889

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 30018 IgR - DNA barcode TLMF Lep 28716) Kurbnesh Fshat, above Khtelle vill. 41.7973N, 20.0668E, 893 m, 8.VII.2019, leg. Beshkov & Nahirnić, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Almost all of Europe, Turkey, S Siberia (Baldizzone 2019a). First record for Albania.

C. ditella Zeller, 1849

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 3022 IgR) MT. Mali me Gropa, southern slopes, northwest from Burimas, above Shengjergi, 400 m, 13.VIII.2018, 41°21'34''N, 20°02'38,23''E, leg. Plant, Beshkov & Nahirnić, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Estonia, Central and Southern Europe, North Africa, Ukraine, Crimea, Russia (Lower Volga), Turkey, Caucasus (including Armenia), Iran, Central Asia, Siberia, Altai, Mongolia, and Japan. First record for Albania.

Note: Recent DNA studies have shown that several genetic profiles exist under the name "*ditella*", so the distribution data will have to be reconsidered in the future. (Baldizzone 2024).

C. changaica Reznik, 1975

North Macedonia: 5 ♂ (GP 35221 IgR) Pepelište near Negotino 30.IV.–10.V. 2024, leg., det., coll. Richter.

Distribution: Portugal, Spain, Morocco, Algeria, Crimea, Russia (Lower Volga), Armenia, Jordan, Afghanistan, China (Baldizzone 2024). First record for North Macedonia.

Note: As for the previous species, DNA analysis shows that under the name "*changaica*" are included some species, which will be divided. Therefore, the same considerations on geographical distribution apply.

C. valesianella Zeller, 1849

Albania: 1 ♀ Qark Gjirokastra, Pagri, 450 m, 40.330106, 20.331515, 19.VIII.2015, leg., coll. F. Graf, det. Richter.

Distribution: Spain, France, Italy, Switzerland, Austria, Hungary, Croatia, Serbia, North Macedonia, Bulgaria, Greece, Cyprus, Ukraine, Turkey, Morocco, Iran. First record for Albania.

C. ochrea (Haworth, 1828)

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 35988 IgR) Pogradec Region, between Dardhas and Guri I Kamjes, 1185 m, N40.8561, E020.631, 23.IX.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant; 1 ♀ (GP 36005 IgR), 8 ♂ Korca-Kolonje, Mt.Kuq, below Qarrit pass, near Qarr Village, 903 m, N40.4597, E020.6528, 21.IX.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richer, coll. C. W. Plant; 1 ♂ (GP 36000 IgR) Liqeni Prespa e Vogel, near Tren Village, 858 m, N40.67466, E020.989, 20.IX.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Europe, except northern part (reported only from Sweden), northern Africa, Turkey, Crimea, Russia (Lower Volga),Caucasus (Krasnodar distr., Armenia), Turkmenistan (Baldizzone 2024). First record for Albania.

C. univittella Staudinger, 1880 (Figs 7-8)

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 35986 IgR) Tepelene Region, above Nivice Village, 1150 m, N.40.2679, E019.8864, 04.VII.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Crimea, Anatolia, Caucasus, Armenia, Turkmenistan, Iran, Afghanistan (Baldizzone 1994). First record for Albania.

C. lixella Zeller, 1849

Serbia: 1 ♀ Stara Planina, Babin zub, 1240 m, 29.VII.2022, leg., coll. T. Koren, det. Baldizzone.

Distribution: Almost all of Europe, Russia (Lower Volga), Turkey, Caucasus (including Armenia) (Baldizzone 2024). First record for Serbia.

C. tricolor Walsingham, 1899

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 35957 IgR) Pogradec Region, above Ochrid Lake, below Maja Ahishtes Geges, 1323 m, N40.998, E020.6087, 8.VI.2022, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant; 3 ♂, 4 ♀ (GP 35968-35974 IgR) Pogradec Region, Guri I Kamjes, 1314 m, N40°50'37,5'', E020°37'17,4'', 05.VI.2022, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant; 3 ♂ Tomori Mts., above Ujanik to Abaz Ali 1894 m, N40.6171, E020.1851, 16.VI.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Great Britain, France, Switzerland, Italy, North Macedonia, Greece, Armenia (Baldizzone, 2024). First record for Albania.

C. samarensis (Anikin, 2001)

Bosnia & Herzegovina: 11 ♂ (GP Bldz 17759, 17760, 17761) Blidinje, Masna Luka, 1361 m, 28.VI.2021, leg. T. Koren, det. Baldizzone, coll. Koren and coll. Baldizzone; 4 ♂, ibidem, 2.VII.2021, leg. Koren, coll. Koren and coll. Baldizzone; 1 ♀ (GP Bldz 17758) Blidinje, Mt. Čvrsnica, 1228 m, 2.VII.2021, leg. M. Martinović, det., coll. Baldizzone.

Distribution: Italy, Spain, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Ukraine, Russia, Georgia, Turkey, Kirghizstan (Baldizzone 2023). The above data, not yet published, serve to document the material from Bosnia-Herzegovina.

C. supinella Ortner, 1949

Albania: 2 ♀ (GP35975, 35977 IgR) Pogradec Region, Guri I Kamjes, 1314 m, N40°50'37,5'', E020°37'17,4'', 05.VI.2022, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Belgium, France, Spain, Italy, Austria, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Bulgaria, North Macedonia (Baldizzone 2019a), Montenegro (Richter 2017). First record for Albania.

C. eupepla (Gozmány, 1954)

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 35967 IgR) Prespa Lake, near Globiceni Village, 930 m N40.8455, E020.9243, 04.VI.2022, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Hungary, Macedonia, Spain, France, Greece, Turkey, Russia (Baldizzone & Tabell 2005), Ukraine (Budashkin & Falkovitsh 2007); Bulgaria (Buschmann et al. 2014). First record for Albania.

C. linosyris E. M. Hering, 1937

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 36003 IgR) Korca-Kolonje, Mt.Kuq, below Qarrit pass, near Qarr Village, 903 m, N40.4597, E020.6528, 21.IX.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: France, Italy, Austria, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Romania, Ukraine, Russia (Southern Urals), Algeria (Baldizzone 2019a), Dagestan (Ustjuzhanin et al. 2022), Switzerland (Bolt & Schmid 2024). First record for Albania.

C. goluensis Baldizzone, 1994 (Figs 10-11.)

North Macedonia: 1 ♀ Pepelište near Negotino Serta mountain pasture 12.8.2023, 1 ♀ 17.VIII.2023, leg. det., coll. Richter.

Distribution: Known only from Turkey (Baldizzone 1994). First record for North Macedonia and Europe.

C. deviella Zeller, 1847

Albania: 1 ♀ Fier, Divjakë, 3 m, 40.989817, 19.496864, 31.V.2023, leg., coll. F. Graf, det. Richter.

Distribution: Great Britain, Denmark, Holland, Belgium, France, Portugal, Spain, Italy, Sardinia, Sicily, Germany, Poland, Bulgaria, Greece, Russia (Lower Volga), Tunisia (Baldizzone, 2019a). First record for Albania.

C. daglarica Baldizzone & Tabell, 1999 (Figs 12-15.)

North Macedonia: 1 ♀ Prilep, Monastir Treskavec, 23.V.2023 ex larva, leg., det., coll. Richter.
Distribution: Turkey (Baldizzone & Tabell 1999), Bulgaria (Richter 2017). First record for North Macedonia.

Bionomy: Until now, the host plant and the larval case of this species were unknown. The first author discovered some larval cases for the first time on 16. VI. 2016, without obtaining adults, and for the second time on 22.VI.2022, from which only one adult emerged.

Larvae live on flowers and seeds of *Minuartia* sp., cf. *recurva* (Caryophyllaceae), from mid-June. After overwintering they are still active, but probably no longer feed. Only one specimen emerged, which still allowed the species to be identified. The larval case is brown, made of silk, with a wrinkled appearance, 4.5 mm long, with an oral opening angled at about 25° and a trilobed anal opening. Adults are found from May until the first ten days of June and are attracted by light

C. lessinica Baldizzone, 1980

Slovenia: 4 ♀ (GP Bldz, 18237) Trnovski gozd, Kovk, 930 m, 11.VIII.2024, leg. G. Baldizzone & S. Gomboc, det., coll. Baldizzone.

Distribution: Southern France, Italy, Croatia, North Macedonia, Hungary, Bulgaria (Richter 2017; Baldizzone 2019a). First record for Slovenia.

C. riffelensis Rebel, 1913

Albania: 3 ♂ (GP 35946, 36024 IgR) Berat, Tomor Mountain below the muslim Shrine at 2380 metres, at mvl. 40.38.08N,20.09.44E, 11.VIII.2018, leg., coll. C. W. Plant, det. Richter.

1 ♀ (GP 36004 IgR) Korca-Kolonje, Mt. Kuq, below Qarrit pass, near Qarr Village, 903 m, N40.4597, E020.6528, 21.IX.2024, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić-Beshkova, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: Spain, France, Italy, Austria, Switzerland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, North Macedonia, Latvia, Estonia, Russia, Ukraine, Turkey, Iran (Baldizzone 2019a), Croatia (Baldizzone & Richter 2022). First record for Albania.

C. depunctella Toll, 1961

Croatia: 1 ♂ (GP 35726 IgR) Omiš, 3.VII.2024 leg., coll. A. Laštůvka, det. Richter.

Distribution: North Macedonia, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece. The second locality recorded confirms the species' occurrence in Croatia.

C. carsica Baldizzone, 2010

Slovenia: 1 ♂ (GP Bldz 17675) Primorska, Pivška kotina, Bač, 727 m, 27.VIII.2021, leg. B. Zadavec & S. Polak, det. Baldizzone, coll. Zadavec.

Distribution: The species was described from north-eastern Italy (Venezia Giulia) and was later discovered in Croatia (Richter & Pastorális 2015). First record for Slovenia.

C. thurneri Glaser, 1969

Slovenia: 1 ♀ (GP Bldz, 18238) Trnovski gozd, Kovk, 930 m, 11.VIII.2024, leg. G. Baldizzone & S. Gomboc, det., coll. Baldizzone.

Distribution: France, Italy, Croatia, Macedonia, Bulgaria (Baldizzone 2019a), recently reported from Spain (Gastón 2024). First record for Slovenia.

C. pseudociconiella Toll, 1952

Croatia: 1 ♀ (GP Bldz 10209) Is. Krk, Misučajnica, 15.VIII.1989, leg., det., coll. Baldizzone.

Distribution: Italy, Sardinia, Austria, Slovakia, Croatia, North Macedonia, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Ukraine, Crimea, Russia (Lower Volga, Central Siberia), Turkey, Caucasus, China (Baldizzone 2019a). The above record, the only one known for Croatia, was accidentally omitted in the publication on Coleophoridae from the island of Krk (Baldizzone 2019b).

C. tyrrhaenica Amsel, 1952

Croatia: 1 ♀ (GP Bldz 17678) Is. Cres, Cres, 23.VII.2021, leg., coll. B. Zadavec, det. Baldizzone.

Distribution: France, Sardinia, Italy, Croatia, Slovakia, Hungary, Bulgaria, Macedonia, Greece, Ukraine, Crimea, Russia (Lower Volga), Caucasus (Baldizzone 2019a). Previously the species had been generically included in the fauna of the former Yugoslavia (Baldizzone 1996). The discovery of the Cres specimen confirms its presence in Croatia.

C. bornicensis Fuchs, 1886 (Figs 16-18.)

North Macedonia: 4 ♂ (GP 32424, 32427, 33609, 33760 IgR), 8 ♀ (GP 32425, 32426 IgR) Galičica NP, Tomoros Mt, 1776 m, 22.-24.VII.2022, leg., det., coll. Richter.

5 ♂ (GP34300, 34302, 34304, 34305 IgR), 6 ♀ (GP 34297, 34298, 34306, 34309, 34310 IgR) Galičica NP, Tomoros Mt., 1776 m, 2.-3.VIII.2023, leg., det., coll. Richter.

1 ♂ (GP 32448 IgR) Galičica NP Dva Topola 1498 m, 21.VII.2022, Richter leg.

1 ♀ (GP 32440 IgR) Galičica Asan Gjura, 1496 m, 27.VII.2022, leg., det., coll. Richter.

Distribution: Netherlands, Germany, Slovakia, Hungary, Crimea, Turkey (Richter & Šima 2015), Belgium, France (Martin 2021). First record for North Macedonia.

C. dianthi Herrich-Schäffer, 1855

Albania: 1 ♀ Gjirokastër, oberhalb Erind, 842 m, N 40.172307 E 20.168844, 10.VIII.2024, leg., coll. F. Graf, det. Richter.

Distribution: Almost all of Europe, Crimea, Russia (Lower Volga), Caucasus (including Armenia), Turkey, Iraq, Iran, Turkmenistan, Transbaikalia, and Southern Siberia up to Altai, Japan (Baldizzone 2024). First record for Albania.

[271] ***C. texanella*** Chambers, 1878

Albania: 1 ♀ Ksamil, 20.IX.2009, leg., coll. K. Bond, det. Richter.

Distribution: Species native to North America, accidentally introduced in Europe, where it is rapidly spreading. Data are known for Great Britain, Denmark, Holland, Belgium, France, Portugal, Spain, Italy, Sardinia, Sicily, Germany, Poland, Bulgaria, Greece, Russia (Lower Volga), Tunisia (Baldizzone 2019a), Cyprus (Barton 2015), Spain (Gastón & Vives Moreno 2020), Morocco (Tabell et al. 2023); Hungary (Tóth et al. 2024). First record for Albania.

C. salicorniae Heinemann & Wocke, 1876

Albania: 1 ♂, 2 ♀ Qark Fier, Divjakë, 2 m, N 40.987646, E 19.496382, 18.VIII.2015, leg. det., coll. F. Graf.

1 ♀ Qark Fier, Divjakë, 4 m, N 40.954339 E 19.472914, 1.IX.2024, leg. det., coll. F. Graf.

Distribution: Almost all of Europe, the Canary Islands, Morocco, Tunisia, Egypt, Cyprus, Turkey, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Siberia, Iran, and China (Baldizzone 2019a). This is the first record for Albania.

C. onopordiella Zeller, 1849

Albania: 1 ♂ (GP 35995 IgR) Tomori Mountain Below Tomori I Madh (above Polican) 686 m: 15.6.2024, N40.6955: E 20.0814, leg. S. Beshkov & A. Nahirnić, det. Richter, coll. C. W. Plant.

Distribution: First record for Albania. Recent DNA studies have shown that several genetic profiles exist under the name "*onopordiella*", so the distribution data will have to be reconsidered in the future. (Baldizzone 2024). As "*onopordiella*" species complex, there is data from southern France, central and southern Italy, Austria, Poland, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Hungary, Romania, Macedonia, Greece, Palestine, Jordan, Turkey, Caucasus (including Armenia), Syria, Iran (Baldizzone 2024).

[283] ***C. nemesi*** (Căpușe, 1970)

Albania: 1 ♀ Qark Vlora, Zvërnec, 6 m, 40.506025, 19.417736, 31.VIII.2024, leg., coll. F.

Graf., det. Baldizzone.

Distribution: Italy (Adriatic coast), Croatia, Albania, Greece, Romania (Black Sea) (Baldizzone 2019a).

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Figs 1–8. 1. Galičica NP, Tomoros Mt.; 2. Prilep, Manastir Treskavec; 3. *Coleophora avellanae*, adult; 4. *Coleophora avellanae*, gen. ap. Male; 5. *Coleophora felixella*, adult; 6. *Coleophora felixella*, gen. ap. Male; 7. *Coleophora univittella*, adult; 8. *Coleophora univittella*, gen. ap. Male.

Figs 9–12. 9. *Coleophora univittella*, gen. ap. female; 10. *Coleophora goluensis*, adult; 11. *Coleophora goluensis*, gen. ap. female; 12. *Coleophora daglarica*, adult.

Figs 13–18. 13. *Coleophora daglarica*, gen. ap. Female; 14. *Coleophora daglarica*, larval case; 15. *Minuartia* sp. (with larva *C. daglarica*), 16. *Coleophora bornicensis*, adult; 17. *Coleophora bornicensis*, gen. ap. male (17a variation); 18. *Coleophora bornicensis*, gen ap. female

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